

TECHNISCHE
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Data management plan (DMP)

Analysis of global emissions and natural disasters

EOSCSecretariat.eu

Version	Effective date	Description of document/changes
1.0	10/05/2023	First version of DMP – created for start of project
2.0	14/05/2023	Final version of DMP

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List of acronyms

DMP	data management plan
RDM	research data management
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Introduction

Science Europe practical guide, FAIR data

A DMP is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions.

For writing this DMP, we followed [the recommendations of Science Europe](#) as they reflect the guidelines agreed upon by the major funders in Europe.

To make our data FAIR, they generally will be treated according to the following criteria:

- We will make our data findable, by uploading it to a data repository that provides a persistent identifier, and adding relevant metadata.
- We will make our data accessible by providing open access to data, wherever possible. In cases, where open access is not possible, we will provide meaningful metadata plus contact information for access requests.
- We will make our data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain by using the same file formats, schemas and vocabularies. We will provide good documentation for all our datasets.
- We will make our data reusable by adding metadata and comprehensive Readme files to all published datasets. The descriptions include details on the methodology used, analytical and procedural information. In case of publication, licenses for code and data will always be assigned and clearly marked.

Relevant Policies and Guidelines

- TU Wien Policy for Research Data Management: <https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Directives%20and%20Regulations%20of%20the%20Rectorate/Policy%20for%20Research%20Data%20Management.pdf>
- TU Wien Code of Conduct – Rules to Ensure Good Scientific Practice: <https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Directives%20and%20Regulations%20of%20the%20Rectorate/Code%20of%20Conduct%20E2%80%93%20Rules%20to%20Ensure%20Good%20Scientific%20Practice.pdf>
- Directives and Regulations of the TU Wien Rectorate: <https://www.tuwien.at/en/tu-wien/organisation/central-divisions/data-protection-and-document-management/directives-regulations/>
- TU Wien Data Protection: <https://www.tuwien.at/en/tu-wien/organisation/central-divisions/data-protection-and-document-management/data-protection-at-tu-wien>
- European Commission's document on Ethics and Data Protection: https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/5_h2020_ethics_and_data_protection.pdf
- Other (e.g. from a project partner)

1. Data description

1a Lists of datasets that will be reused or produced

Produced datasets

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	Worldwide CO2 emissions and natural disasters from 1960 to 2021 (PDF)	Images	PDF	<100 MB	no
P2	Worldwide CO2 emissions and natural disasters from 1960 to 2021 (CSV)	Structured text	CSV	<100 MB	no

Produced code

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
C1	plot.py	Source code	PY	<100 MB	no

Reused datasets

dataset ID	title	PID (e.g. DOI) or source	rights (e.g. license)	contains sensitive data
R1	Global Carbon Atlas	http://doi.org/10.17616/R3434K	other	no
R2	EM-DAT	http://doi.org/10.17616/R3QQ1X	other	no

1b Data generation and reuse

Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

The provided research data will be filtered and cumulated to create a dataset which lists the total global CO2 emissions as well as the total number of natural disasters for each year from 1960 to 2021.

This is done using the python script C1 (found in 10.5281/zenodo.7934702) which has the following requirements:

Interpreter: Python >= 3.10

Modules:

- pandas 2.0.1 (data analysis and manipulation)
- matplotlib 3.7.1 (data visualization)
- openpyxl 3.1.2 (reading/writing .xlsx files)

This script produces a CSV file (10.5281/zenodo.7934714) containing the data described above as well as a PDF file (10.5281/zenodo.7934732) containing a plot which visualizes the data.

The datasets R1 and R2 used as input data have both custom licenses. R1 gives open access to their data and allows non-commercial use while R2 restricts data access but also allows the usage for research purposes. Please refer to their respective DOI links for further details about the licences of the input data.

2. Documentation and data quality

2a Data organisation, metadata and documentation

The data is structured into three folders: "src", "res", and "out". The folder "src" contains the source code i.e. the python script which generates the output data as well as a "requirements.txt" file which lists all module dependencies required for this script to run. The folder "res" is used to hold the input data for the python script. It contains two subfolders "co2_emissions" and "natural_disasters" which contain the respective input data as well as a README explaining where the input data is from and how it was modified so that the python script can consume it directly. The folder "out" is used to hold the output data produced by the python script. All these folders are part of a GitHub project (10.5281/zenodo.7934702) where the versioning of everything mentioned is taking place.

As there are no domain specific metadata standards applicable, we will provide a README file with an explanation of all values and terms used at project level.

Additionally, we will provide common metadata such as title, description or keywords when publishing data in open access repositories. In such a case, we will follow the default template provided by the repository, such as Data Cite Metadata, Dublin Core or Zenodo.

As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.

A README will be provided which explains where the input data comes from and that a python script is used to create the output data. The python script contains comments for nearly each line so it should be possible to validate the data analysis. In case of re-usability a DOI is assigned to the project containing the python script C1 which generates the data, as well as to the output data.

2b Data quality control

The following data quality checks will be done: peer review of data.

3. Storage and backup during research process

3a Storage and backup facilities

For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data will be ensured by the project manager in cooperation with the responsible representative of TU.it. The infrastructure of TU Wien will not be used for this purpose.

P1 (Worldwide CO2 emissions and natural disasters from 1960 to 2021 (PDF)), R1 (Global Carbon Atlas), R2 (EM-DAT), P2 (Worldwide CO2 emissions and natural disasters from 1960 to 2021 (CSV)) and C1 (plot.py) will be stored in GitHub. External storage will be used because the access to institutional storage options is only given to staff members.

P1 (Worldwide CO2 emissions and natural disasters from 1960 to 2021 (PDF)), R1 (Global Carbon Atlas), R2 (EM-DAT), P2 (Worldwide CO2 emissions and natural disasters from 1960 to 2021 (CSV)) and C1 (plot.py) will be stored in Zenodo. External storage will be used because the access to institutional storage options is only given to staff members.

3b Data security and protection of sensitive data

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies listed in the introduction of this document. At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien (Verena Dolovai), and the DMP will be updated.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P1	writing	reading only	reading only
P2	writing	reading only	reading only
R1	writing	reading only	reading only
R2	writing	reading only	reading only

All incidents will be handled individually by an incident response team that is maintaining the affected service.

4. Legal and ethical requirements

4a Personal data

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien (Verena Dolovai), and the DMP will be updated.

4b Intellectual property rights and ownership

There are no legal restrictions on the processing and disclosure of the produced data. However, this does not apply to the input data R1 and R2 used for this experiment.

4c Ethical issues

No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise.

5. Data sharing and long-term preservation

5a Data publication and access conditions

As far as possible, obtained datasets will be published in repositories. Details on access conditions, reuse licenses, reasons for restrictions, etc. are collected in the table below.

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Open		2023-05-14	GitHub / Zenodo	10.5281/zenodo.7934732	CC0 1.0
P2	Open		2023-05-14	GitHub / Zenodo	10.5281/zenodo.7934714	CC0 1.0
C1	Open		2023-05-14	GitHub / Zenodo	10.5281/zenodo.7934702	MIT

The repositories used in this project are described in the following paragraph:

GitHub is a web-based platform that provides version control and collaboration tools for software development projects. It allows users to host their code repositories, track changes, and work together with others. While GitHub is primarily known for hosting code, it can also serve as a valuable option to store research data. GitHub offers version control, which means that every change made to a repository is tracked, allowing researchers to easily see and revert to previous versions if needed. This helps maintain a clear history of changes and supports reproducibility in research. GitHub also provides collaboration features that enable multiple researchers to work together on a project. It allows for seamless collaboration, as team members can contribute, review, and discuss code and data within the platform. This fosters a collaborative and transparent research environment.

Zenodo is an open-access repository that specializes in archiving and sharing scientific research data. It provides researchers with a reliable and long-term storage solution for their data and offers integration options with platforms like GitHub.

Methods or software needed to access and use data: Reusing the data does not require any specific software tools. The produced data is a .csv and a .pdf file which can both be used with a various amount of software. The .pdf file is meant for embedding in a document while die .csv file is meant to be used for further research/analysis.

5b Long-term preservation and deletion of data

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)	foreseeable research uses and/or users
P1	GitHub / Zenodo	10 years	Students and general public because the data gives a simple overview rather than detailed insights.
P2	GitHub / Zenodo	10 years	

Overview of (unpublished) data that will be deleted:

dataset ID	kind/name of data	date of deletion	reason for deletion	responsible person

6. RDM responsibilities and resources

6a RDM-roles and responsibilities

The PI will direct the data management process overall, with the research assistants responsible for ensuring metadata production, day-to-day cross-checks, back-up and other quality control activities are maintained. The lead country researchers will be responsible for routine supervision of the dataset development.

6b Resources

There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR.

Cost name	Cost type	Description	Unit	Value
Estimated total costs				0